

Synthesis of Schiff Bases, 2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 2,3-Disubstituted-4-thiazolidinones as Antifungal Agents

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SCHIFF bases are associated with diverse biocidal activities¹ probably by virtue of a toxophoric C=N linkage. Several 1,3,4-oxadiazoles² and 4-thiazolidinones³ are known to exhibit significant biological activities. These observations stimulated us to synthesise the title compounds with a view to screening their antifungal activity.

Reaction of α -aryloxypropionyl hydrazines with aromatic aldehydes gave the Schiff bases (2a-i), which on oxidative cyclisation with bromine in glacial acetic acid in presence of fused sodium acetate furnished 1,3,4-oxadiazoles⁴ (3a-i). The absence of NH and C=O peaks in the ir spectra of 3 suggested the cyclisation of 2 to 3. The cycloaddition of thioglycollic acid to Schiff bases in dioxane yielded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones⁵ (4a-i). The absence of C=N peak and the presence of ir bands at 1 730 (C=O) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C), and a singlet of enolic OH at 15 ppm in the pmr spectra of 4 confirmed the formation of 4-thiazolidinones (4a-i) (Scheme 1).

a; R=4-Cl, 3-CH₃, R'=H f, R=4-(CH₃)₂C, R'=OH
 b, R=4-Cl, 3-CH₃, R'=Cl g, R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=H
 c, R=4-Cl, 3-CH₃, R'=OH h, R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=Cl
 d, R=4-(CH₃)₂C, R'=H i, R=2,4-(CH₃)₂, R'=OH
 e; R=4-(CH₃)₂C, R'=Cl

Scheme 1

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Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference at 90 MHz. The required hydrazines were prepared by standard method. All the compounds (2-4) showed satisfactory analytical results for N and S.

1- α -(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)propionyl-2-benzylidene hydrazine (2a): A mixture of α -(4-chloro-3-methylphenoxy)propionyl hydrazine (2.28 g, 0.01 mol), benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (74%), m.p. 165° (Found: N, 8.68. C₁₇H₁₇ClN₂O₂ requires: N, 8.85%; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 180 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 030 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 650 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.45-1.55 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.65-4.85 (1H, q, CH), 6.65-7.95 (8H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, s, =CH) and 12.0 (1H, s, NH).

Similarly, other compounds (2b-i) were prepared: 2b (81%), 169°; 2c (79%), 146°; 2d (61%), 163°; 2e (72%), 213°; 2f (80%), 207°; 2g (79%), 152°; 2h (76%), 160°; 2i (78%), 182°.

5- α -(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)ethyl-2-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole⁴ (3a): Bromine (1.76 g, 0.011 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was added slowly to a cooled and stirred slurry of 1- α -(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)propionyl-2-benzylidene hydrazine (3.16 g, 0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (4 g) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml). The mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 h and then poured into water. The separated solid was washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (70%), m.p. 158° (Found: N, 8.62. C₁₇H₁₅ClN₂O₂ requires: N, 8.90%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 510 (C=N), 1 040 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 660 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

Similarly, other compounds (3b-i) were prepared: 3b (58%), 122°; 3c (64%), 92°; 3d (61%), 138°; 3e (68%), 184°; 3f (73%), 96°; 3g (59%), 138°; 3h (49%), 147°; 3i (70%), 87°.

2-Phenyl-3- α -(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)propionamido-4-thiazolidinone⁵ (4a): A mixture of the Schiff base (2a; 3.16 g, 0.01 mol) and thioglycollic acid (1.02 g, 0.011 mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The excess dioxane was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice-cold water. The solid, thus obtained was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, finally with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (81%), m.p. 126° (Found: N, 6.93; S, 8.02. C₁₉H₁₉ClN₂O₃S requires: N, 7.17; S, 8.19%; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 220 (NH), 1 730 (C=O lactone), 1 680 (C=O), 1 050 and 1 240 (=C-O-C), 700 (C-S-C) and 660 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.55-1.65

(3H, d, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, SCH₂CO), 4.75–4.95 (1H, q, CH), 5.95 (1H, s, SCHAr), 6.7–7.6 (8H, m, ArH) and 15.0 (1H, s, OH enolic).

Similarly, other compounds (4b–i) were prepared: 4b (81%), 94°; 4c (67%), 82°; 4d (56%), 90°; 4e (48%), 147°; 4f (76%), 155°; 4g (68%), 97°; 4h (55%), 54°; 4i (60%), 125°.

Antifungal activity: Twelve compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against two fungi, viz. *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* by agar-plate technique⁶ at three different concentrations (1000, 100 and 10 ppm). A commercial fungicide Blitox 50 WP, was also screened under similar conditions for comparison.

All the compounds under investigation were significantly toxic to both the fungi at 1000 ppm. They were, however, slightly more active against *H. oryzae* than against *A. niger*. 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles displayed low level of fungicidal activity, whereas their parent Schiff bases and 4-thiazolidinones showed good level of fungicidal activity. Compounds 4a and 4c were found to be relatively more active against both the fungi. The fungicidal activity of compound 4c (86.5% against *H. oryzae*) was quite comparable with commercial fungicide Blitox 50 WP (97%) at 1000 ppm. In general, compounds with chlorine and methyl groups in the aryloxy moiety were more fungicidal.

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